
**A STUDY ON INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS AWARENESS ON MUTUAL FUNDS
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO INSPIRE INDIA WEALTH
PVT, LTD.**

¹Akula Harini ²Dr.K. PUSHPALATHA

¹II MBA Student Engineering college (Autonomous), Secunderabad,
hariniraoakula@gmail.com

²Professor/ Department of MBA, Malla Reddy Engineering college.
pushpa.kamineni@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study examines the level of awareness and perception of individual investors towards mutual funds as an investment option. Mutual funds have emerged as a popular investment avenue due to diversification, professional management, and liquidity. However, awareness among retail investors, especially in Tier-II and Tier-III cities, remains limited. The research is based on primary data collected through structured questionnaires from individual investors across different age groups, income levels, and occupations. Key areas studied include knowledge of types of mutual funds, risk-return factors, SIP, NAV, expense ratio, and tax benefits. Secondary data from AMFI reports, journals, and financial websites was also used. Findings reveal that while most investors have heard of mutual funds, detailed understanding of fund categories, risks, and performance evaluation is low. Investors prefer fixed deposits and insurance due to perceived safety. Major factors influencing mutual fund investment are returns, brand of AMC, and advice from agents or friends. Lack of financial literacy, fear of market risk, and complex procedures are key barriers. The study concludes that awareness programs, simplified processes, and investor education by AMCs and regulators are essential to increase mutual fund penetration. Enhancing financial literacy can help investors make informed decisions and improve participation in capital markets.

Key Words: Mutual Funds, Individual Investors, Investor Awareness, Financial Literacy, SIP, NAV, Risk-Return, Investment Behaviour, AMFI, Retail Investors

Introduction:

The four fundamental parts of the Indian financial system are the financial market, financial institutions. Each and every one of them is crucial to the efficient allocation and movement of finances. The provision of effective services to the capital market is the primary goal of the Indian financial system. The second generation of reforms has seen a massive expansion of the Indian capital market. The idea of LPG was introduced in 1991 as the first generation of reforms. (Liberalization, privatization, Globalization)

WHAT IS A MUTUAL FUND?

A mutual fund is a collection of funds managed by a trust that is used to invest the savings of several participants who have similar financial objectives, such as dividend income and capital growth. The funds thus obtained are thereafter used to purchase shares, debentures, and foreign exchange. When investors make an investment, they receive units based on the unit value, or NAV (net asset value). The best kind of investment for an average person is a mutual fund. It allows them to participate in diversified portfolio management. The primary goal of the fund manager is to take undervalued stocks and sell them off when they rise in value. The fund manager has a strong research staff and

professionally manages both foreign and Indian stocks. Focus on the risk-return trade-off by fund managers, who diversify their portfolios to minimise risk and maximise return. The lowest cost of the mutual fund unit is its most prevalent feature.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

A mutual fund is an investment vehicle that is made by combining money that has been collected from various individuals to buy stocks, bonds, money market instruments, and other comparable assets. While many are unaware of this type of investment, others have profited from it. Due to their lack of understanding of this mode, some investors

put money into it in the hopes of earning returns greater than those offered by time deposits in commercial banks. If the anticipated yield does not materialize as expected or worsens, these investors leave the mode and discourage others from joining. Mutual funds are currently one of the most profitable investment options available to investors. The task at hand was to research and gauge the city's population's level of mutual fund awareness. The study analyses the investors according to their age, financial goals, and other factors. It also looked at how mutual funds (MF) fit into the spectrum of investment options accessible to investors and the historical performance of different schemes offered by the active AMCs in the Indian market based on time and NAV. In order to assist investors and advisors in selecting the appropriate portfolio. The purpose of this study is to determine the level of investment or knowledge of mutual funds and the best ways to introduce them to prospective buyers.

1.2 NEED FOR THE STUDY:

- This project's primary goal was to learn more about mutual funds and how they operate. It helps in learning in-depth information on the mutual fund business, including its history, development, and prospects.
- The research consists entirely of a broad examination of investors' awareness of mutual funds.
- The study will provide information about different investors' investment awareness of mutual funds, which helps the organization in identifying different investors' awareness while improving mutual fund marketing.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To examine the awareness level of mutual fund investors.
- To examine the most recent developments in India's mutual fund industry.
- To provide a brief summary of the advantages of investing in mutual fund

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The purpose of the study is to determine investors' priorities, preferences, and level of awareness regarding various mutual fund schemes. The study's scope is restricted to investors who reside in India due to several constraints. Stratified sampling is used to gather data for the study from 150 investors in the sample.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Both primary and secondary data were used for creating this report; however, as primary data gathering is a major role in attitude research, it was given more weight.

One of the most significant applications of research methodology is its assistance in problem identification, information gathering, analysis, and giving alternative solutions. Additionally, it helps in gathering the crucial data that upper management needs in order to support them in making better decisions-both essential and daily.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

- This study just looks at certain customers in Bengaluru. Therefore, conclusions and recommendations drawn from this study cannot be applied to the whole population.
- The sample size of 100 is quite small and insufficient for examining the country's consumer awareness.
- We are unable to identify the best option because respondents did not fill out the questionnaire with sincerity or attention.
- While sampling is a convenient procedure, personal bias may arise. Therefore, a perfect outcome is unattainable.
- DATA COLLECTION METHODS

1. PRIMARY DATA:

This type of data has been collected from the investors with the help of a Questionnaire

2. SECONDARY DATA

The secondary data relating to net resources mobilized by banks and financial institution sponsored mutual funds, this kind of information is gathered from a variety of sources, including magazines, newspapers, RBI reports, AMFI reports, SEBI annual reports, studies of the securities market, examination of previously published works by various writers in relevant fields, and other investment publications.

SAMPLING UNIT:

The sampling unit for the study will be the investors and non-investors of Bengaluru city

SAMPLING METHOD:

The sample will be collected by in-person meetings, official conversations, and the completion of a written questionnaire. Through the use of statistical or mathematical methods, the data has been examined

STATISTICAL TOOLS USED:

Various statistical tools have been used in the research process to obtain specific and significant data and outcomes. Factor analysis has been used for primary data, and score assignment has been used to determine the relative importance of each element in categories where respondents are asked to rank various factors. Exponential growth rates have been computed for secondary data.

SAMPLE SIZE:

The search consists of the 100-sample size.

REVIEWS OF LITERATURE:

1. Sambath Kumar (2018)

Sambath Kumar highlights that the Indian mutual fund industry has grown into a transparent, self-driven, and automated market with strong investor protection and disclosure norms. Global integration is evident through foreign investments, Indian firms listing abroad, and international AMCs operating in India. India ranks second only to the UK in investor count, with 24 regional listed firms showing the market's depth.

2. Mital Bhayani (2017)

Mital Bhayani observes that mutual fund growth in India is concentrated among institutional investors, T-15 cities, and debt schemes. A large section of potential investors remains untapped. The main challenge is reaching diverse investor groups beyond metros. Improving financial literacy and awareness can encourage retail participation, while expanding distribution networks beyond big cities is key to broader growth.

3. John C. Bogle (2021 Updated Edition)

The updated edition of Bogle's Common Sense on Mutual Funds offers fresh insights on mutual fund performance, risk, and investment strategy. It remains a vital guide for intelligent investing, helping investors understand fund selection and long-term wealth creation through a common-sense, low-cost approach.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

• **TABLE No. 4.1: "GENDER" OF THE RESPONDENTS**

Response	No. Of Respondents	% of Respondents
Male	64	64%
Female	36	36%
Total	100	100%

Analysis: From the all respondents there are 64% are men and 36% are women. It indicates that there are more men than women.

GRAPH No. 4.1: "GENDER" OF THE RESPONDENTS

R ESPONSE

■ Male ■ Female

Interpretation : It is evident from the preceding graph that 36% of people are female and 64% are male. According to the study above, men make up the majority of the responses

TABLE No. 4.2: "AGE GROUP" OF THE RESPONDENTS

Response	No.OfRespondents	% OfRespondents
Below-20	9	9%
20 -30	82	82%
31 -40	7	7%
Above-40	2	2%
Total	100	100%

Analysis: From the above Table, it is cleared that 82% belong to the age group of 20 - 30 years, 9% belong to the age group of Below-20 years, 7% respondents belong to the age group of 31-40 years and 2% respondents belong to the age group of 40 & above years

R ESPONSE

Interpretation: From the above Graph, it is cleared that 82% belong to the age group of 20–30years, 9% belong to the age group of Below - 20 years, 7% respondents belong to the age group of 31 - 40 years and 2% respondents belong to the age group of 40 & above years.

TABLE No. 4.3: “MARITAL STATUS” OF THE RESPONDENTS

Response	No.OfRespondents	% OfRespondents
Married	14	14%
Unmarried	86	86%
Total	100	100%

Analysis: From the above table,It is well known that 86% of people are unmarried whilethe remaining 14% are married. Therefore, the study indicates that the majority of respondents are unmarried.

GRAPH No. 4.3: “MARITAL STATUS” OF THE RESPONDENTS

R E S P O N S E

Interpretation: From the above Graph, It is well known that 86% of people are unmarried while the remaining 14% are married. Therefore, the study indicates that the majority of respondents are unmarried.

TABLE No. 4.4: "HIGHEST QUALIFICATION" OF THE RESPONDENTS

	No.of Respondents	% of Respondents
SSLC	5	5%
PUC	12	12%
Graduate	49	49%
Postgraduate	34	34%
Total	100	100%

Analysis: From the above table, The majority of people's highest qualifications are clearly graduates (49%), postgraduates (34%), PUC (12%), and SSLC (5%).

GRAPH No. 4.4: "HIGHEST QUALIFICATION" OF THE RESPONDENTS

R E S P O N S E

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Interpretation : From the above Graph,The majority of people's highest qualifications are clearly graduates (49%), postgraduates (34%), PUC (12%), and SSLC (5%).

TABLE No. 4.5: "OCCUPATION" OF THE RESPONDENTS

Response	No.OfRespondents	% OfRespondents
Employedfulltime	44	44%
parttime	7	7%
Student	46	46%
Unemployed	3	3%
Total	100	100%

Analysis: From the above table, it is cleared that the majority of the peoples occupations arestudent (46%), Employed full time(44%), Part time (7%) and Unemployed(3%)

GRAPH No. 4.5: "OCCUPATION" OF THE RESPONDENTS

R ESPONSE

Interpretation:From the above Graph, it is cleared that the majority of the Peoples occupations are student (46%), Employed full time (44%), Part time (7%) and Unemployed (3%)

TABLE No. 4.6: "INCOME GROUP" OF THE RESPONDENTS

Response	No.OfRespondents	% OfRespondents
Below-25000	69	69%
25000-35000	24	24%
35000-45000	5	5%
Above-45000	2	2%
Total	100	100%

Analysis: From the above table, it is cleared that the most of the peoples that is 69% belong to the income group of Below-25,000, 24% respondents belong to the income group of 25,000 – 35,000, 5% respondents belong to the income group 35,000–45,000 and 2% respondents belong to the income group of Above – 45,000

GRAPH No. 4.6: “INCOME GROUP ” OF THE RESPONDENTS

R ESPONSE

Interpretation : From the above Graph ,it is cleared that the most of the peoples that is 69% belong to the income group of Below – 25,000, 24% respondents belong to the income group of 25,000 – 35,000, 5% respondents belong to the income group 35,000 – 45,000 and 2% respondents belong to the income group of Above – 45,000

TABLENo.4.7:Classification of Responses of the Respondents Regarding the Statement “Which Of The Following You Are Interested To Invest In?”

Response	No.OfRespondents	% OfRespondents
Mutualfund	46	46%
Share market	16	16%
Both	20	20%
Notinterested above	18	18%
Total	100	100%

Analysis:From the above table,it is cleared that the majority of the peoples Interested to investin Mutual fund(46%), mutual fund and share market (20%), Not interested (18%) andShare market (16%).

GRAPHNo.4.7:Classification of Responses of the Respondents Regarding the Statement “W hich of the following you are Interested to invest in?”

Interpretation: From the above Graph, it is cleared that the majority of the peoples Interested to invest iMutual fund(46%), mutual fund and share market (20%), Not interested (18%) andShare market (16%).

TABLENo.4.8:Classification of Responses of the Respondents Regarding the Statement “Are You Aware

About Mutual Fund?"

Response	No.OfRespondents	% OfRespondents
Yes	82	82%
No	18	18%
Total	100	100%

Analysis: From the above table, it is cleared that the most of the peoples Aware about mutual funds that is Yes (82 %) and No (18%).

GRAPHNo.4.8:Classification of Responses of the Respondents Regarding the Statement "Are You Aware About Mutual Fund?"

Yes No

Interpretation: From the above Graph, it is cleared that the most of the peoples Aware about mutual funds that is Yes (82 %) and No (18%).

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- 82% of all respondents know about mutual funds, while only 18% do not. Out of all respondents, only 54% have made a mutual fund investment.
- Of all respondents, 64% are men and 36% are women. More men are knowledgeable with mutual funds than women.
- People in their 20 - 30 years are more aware than others.
- Among people, students and employees 36% are aware about Mutual Fund. It shows that there is more awareness in students and employees.
- There are 49 respondents who are all graduates among them 40 are aware and 9 are not aware about Mutual Fund.
- There are 34 respondents who are all post graduate among them 26 are aware and 8 are not aware about

Mutual Fund.

- More respondents have their annual income below 25000 and from 28 of them 23% people are prefer invest in Mutual Fund and 5% not.
- From all the respondents 35 respondents have awareness regarding Mutual Fund through advertisement and less number of respondents are aware through distributors.
- 84% of respondents participate in systematic investment plans,where as16% make lump sum investments.
- From all aware respondents 32% respondents have their investment objectives are savings and 26% to provide for retirement.
- 66% of the respondents said they buy mutual fund products online.
- Among allrespondents43% are very satisfiedwith theirinvestment in Mutual Fund and 31%are satisfied with their investment. Only 1% are dissatisfied with their investment.
- Among all the respondents there are 2% of the people says very high risk and 35% of the people says little risk while investing in Mutual Fund.
- From all aware respondents 35 respondents did not invest in Mutual Fund out of 82.
- 46%Among the not investors 20% respondents No particular reason and 18% respondents lack of knowledge.
- There are 40% respondents have interested to invest in Mutual Fund.

• **SUGGESTIONS**

- Following review of the entire data analysis and conclusions ,my recommendations forth sector are displayed below.
- Since many people have heard of mutual funds but are unaware of what they are, the company should educate the public about them through a variety of channels, such as more advertisements, television shows, etc., explaining what they are, how they operate, how to handle them, and what benefits they offer.
- In order to draw in medium-income in dividuals, the businessshould also demon strate the short-term advantages of the liquidity funds.
- According to a poll, banks raise awareness, which encourages mutual fund companies to work with them more.
- The business should also use various strategies to draw in clients who are aware of mutual funds but have not made an investment in them.
- In order to attract customers who are aware of mutual funds but have not yet invested in them, the company needs employ a variety of tactics.
- Information about the tax benefits of investing in mutual funds should be provided by the company.
- The business should disseminate booklets with detailed information on mutual fund schemes and host seminars to educate people about mutual funds.
- Gaining the trust of investors and defending their rights are the shared goals of all mutual fund businesses. To protect the interests of regular investors, the AMFI and SEBI should enact stringent rules and regulations in this regard.If these guidelines are not being appropriately followed, aprovision for punishment should be

included for those who break them.

- Some investors expressed dissatisfaction, claiming that brokers and sub-brokers are more focused on the incentives that the corporations give them to sell more schemes. Therefore, it is imperative that they carry out their responsibilities without most care and thoroughness and refrain from misleading the investors. Investors should receive accurate and timely information from brokers, sub-brokers, and agents. For the benefit to investors, they need to be up to date on the most recent developments in the market.
- It is necessary to take action to improve the investors' self-esteem and confidence. This can be accomplished by teaching investors about mutual fund investing and by using suitable communication. They should be given timely and accurate information through several channels of communication so they may learn about the most recent industry trends

- **CONCLUSION**

- Investors have access to a wide range of investment options in the financial markets nowadays. Corporate bonds, debentures, bank deposits, post office schemes, and other options are available to investors. However, investors now choose portfolio managers to make investments for them. Experts in stock market operations, these portfolio managers allocate and provide clients with the bare minimum of guaranteed returns. Many organisations are currently occupied with offering investors wealth management services. However, these services are highly expensive. Therefore, to assist investors, mutual funds offer both small and large investors a safe haven.

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- **BOOK REFERRED**

- “The intelligent investor” by Benjamin Graham, a classic investment guide that covers a wide range of topics including mutual funds
- “Common Sense on Mutual Funds” by John C. Bogle, the founder of the Vanguard Group, shares his insights on mutual funds.
- “Mutual Funds for Dummies” by Eric Tyson, a beginner – friendly guide that explains the basics of mutual funds in a clear and concise manner.
- “The Investor’s Manifesto” by William Bernstein, this book offers a comprehensive overview of investing including mutual funds.
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